

Synthesis of some New Fluorine containing Oxazoles, Oxadiazoles, Thiadiazoles and Triazines^ψ

VIJAI N. PATILAK*, MAHENDRA K. GOYAL, MEENAKSHI JAIN and KRISHNA C. JOSHI

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-300 004

Manuscript received 31 March 1992, revised 16 October 1992, accepted 8 February 1993

Treatment of fluorine containing phenacyl bromides with urea or substituted arylureas afforded the corresponding 2-(amino/*N*-arylamino)-4-(fluoroaryl)oxazoles, and with ammonium acetate in glacial acetic acid yielded 2-methyl-4-(fluoroaryl)oxazoles. Fluorinated arylglyoxals on refluxing with semicarbazide or thiosemicarbazide afforded arylglyoxalsemicarbazones/or thiosemicarbazones, cyclisation of these with potassium carbonate in aqueous ethanol afforded 1,2,4-triazines, while with sodium acetate and sodium bromide in acetic acid yielded 1,3,4-oxadiazoles/or -thiadiazoles. The structures of the compounds have been established by analytical and ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral data.

The physiological activities of oxazoles, their 2-amino and *N*-arylamino derivatives and 1,2,4-triazines are well-documented in the literature¹. In continuation of our earlier work²⁻⁴, we now report the synthesis of some new fluorine containing 2-(amino/*N*-arylamino)-4-(fluoroaryl)oxazoles (**5**), 2-methyl-4-(fluoroaryl)oxazoles (**6**), arylglyoxalthiosemicarbazones and semicarbazones (**8**), 1,2,4-triazines (**9**) and 1,3,4-oxadiazole/or -thiadiazole (**10**) (Schemes 1 and 2).

Results and Discussion

Compounds **2a-h** and **3a-h** were prepared by standard procedures and were characterised on the basis of physical, spectral and/or analytical data, which are in harmony with the values reported earlier²⁻⁴.

The ir spectra of compounds **5a-h** and **6a-c** exhibited a strong band at 1 050-1 120 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C) which is in harmony with the proposed structures. In addition, another band was observed at 3 350-3 420 cm⁻¹ (NH or NH₂). In the ¹H nmr spectra of these compounds, all the aromatic protons resonate in the range δ 7.7-8.0 =CH-O proton at δ 2.45-2.5, NH₂ proton at δ 3.1-3.12 and CH₃ proton

at δ 2.12-2.33. Further confirmation of the structures of the compounds were obtained by mass spectral data where molecular ions peaks *M*⁺ at *m/z* 178 (63.92%) **5a** and 211/213 (80.0/26.66%) **6c**.

Compound **7** showed two characteristic ir bands at 1 590-1 850 cm⁻¹ (C=O). An additional band observed at 3 450-3 570 cm⁻¹ is due to the polymeric association of OH group. The ¹H nmr spectra of **7** showed a resonance signal at δ 7.9-8.1 due to -HC=O and at δ 3.2-3.4 due to H₂O in their hydrates. Further confirmation of the formation of arylglyoxals was obtained from mass spectral studies.

The ir spectra of compounds **8a-g** showed characteristic peaks at 3 100-3 360 (NH and NH₂), 1 590-1 620 (C=O) and 1 020-1 250 cm⁻¹ (C=S). It showed ¹H nmr resonance signals at δ 11.0 (NH), 10.2-10.6 (NH₂) and 8.0-8.1 (ArH). Mass spectra of compounds **8a** and **8b** showed molecular ion peaks at *m/z* 225 (62.06%) and 239 (68.27%) respectively, corresponding to their molecular masses.

Compounds **9a-c** exhibited ir bands at 1 640 (NH-C=O) and 3 560 cm⁻¹ (OH) and in the ¹H nmr spectra, it showed resonance signals at δ 12.38

^ψAbstracts: '12th International Symposium on Fluorine Chemistry, Santa Cruz, California, U.S.A., 1988.

(OH), 9.66 (NH), 6.88–7.89 (ArH) and 2.20 (CH₃). Further, the mass spectra of **9a** and **9b** showed reasonably intense molecular ion peak at *m/z* 191 (74.2%) and 205 (42.3%) respectively.

Compounds **10a,b** exhibited ir bands at 3 520 (NH₂), 1 650 (C=O) and 1 610 cm⁻¹ (–N=C). The ¹H nmr spectra showed multiplet at δ 7.0–9.0 (ArH and NH₂). Further support was obtained by mass spectral data as molecular ion peaks *M*⁺ at *m/z* 207 (52.10%) of **10a** and 223 (64.42%) of **10b** correspond to their molecular masses. The resonance signals corresponding to NH₂ and NH or OH have been confirmed by D₂O exchange studies.

Experimental

All the m.ps. and b.ps. are uncorrected. The ir spectra (nujol/KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrometer, the ¹H nmr spectra (TFA and CDCl₃) on a Bruker HX (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as external reference and the mass spectra on Kratos MS-30 and a MS-50 spectrometers operating at an ionisation potential of 70 eV. Tlc has done on silica gel plates to monitor the purity of the compounds using various solvent systems.

Fluorinated arylhydrocarbons (1): Fluorobenzene, *o*-chlorofluorobenzene, *o*-fluorotoluene, and *p*-fluorotoluene were prepared from the corresponding aromatic amines (0.01 mol) by the Balz-Schiemann reaction⁵.

Fluorinated aryl methyl ketones (2): 4-Fluoroacetophenone, 3-chloro-4-fluoroacetophenone, 4-fluoro-3-methylacetophenone and 2-fluoro-5-methylacetophenone were prepared by the reported methods⁶.

Fluorinated phenacyl bromides (3): 4-Fluorophenacyl bromide, 3-chloro-4-fluorophenacyl bromide and 4-fluoro-3-methylphenacyl bromide were prepared⁷ from fluorinated aryl methylketones (0.01 mol) on treatment with calculated quantities of bromine (0.01 mol) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (5–10 ml) at 32–40°.

Arylureas (4): Phenylurea, 4-chlorophenylurea and 4-methylphenylurea were prepared from the

corresponding aromatic amines by the sodium cyanate method⁸.

2-Amino-4-(4-fluorophenyl)oxazoles (5): A mixture of arylurea (1.20 g, 0.02 mol) and 4-fluorophenacyl bromide (2.17 g, 0.02 mol) was refluxed in absolute ethanol (70 ml) for 8 h with occasional shaking on a water-bath. The reaction mixture was then cooled to afford the sticky product which was washed with ammonium hydroxide solution (30 ml), and extracted with ether (2 × 50 ml). The ethereal solution was dried (Na₂SO₄) and filtered. Removal of the solvent afforded **5a** which was purified by distillation under reduced pressure. The physical data of the compounds are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **5** AND **6***

Compd no	Substituents in Ar	R ²	Yield %	B p °C/10rr
5a	4-F	H	57	105/5
b	4-F	C ₆ H ₅	50	90/4
c	4-F	4-XH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	42	65/2
d	4-F	4-Cl-X ₆ H ₄	55	85/5
e	4-F, 3-CH ₃	H	50	85/5
f	4-F, 3-XH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	50	95/5
g	3-Cl, 4-F	H	56	120 ^o
h	3-Cl, 4-F	4-Xλ-C ₆ H ₄	50	105 ^o
6a	4-F	CH ₃	48	80/5
b	4-F, 3-XH ₃	ClH ₃	55	90/2
c	3-Cl, 4-F	CH ₃	48	120/5

* All compounds gave satisfactory N, C and H analyses ^aM p (°C)

4-(4-Fluorophenyl)-2-methyloxazole (6): A mixture of ammonium acetate (1.54 g, 0.02 mol) and 4-fluorophenacyl bromide (2.17 g, 0.02 mol) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid (50–60 ml) for 5 h. On cooling, the solid mass deposited was filtered. The filtrate was extracted with ether (2 × 50 ml), washed successively with sodium carbonate solution (20 ml) and water. The combined ether extract was dried (Na₂SO₄) and distilled under reduced pressure to give **6a**. The physical data of the compounds are recorded in Table 1.

Fluorinated arylglyoxals (7): 4-Fluorophenylglyoxal, 3-chloro-4-fluorophenylglyoxal, 4-fluoro-3-

Scheme 1

methylphenylglyoxal and 2-fluoro-5-methylphenylglyoxal were prepared by the reported method² by selenium dioxide oxidation of the corresponding aryl methylketones in dioxan-water (1 : 4) medium.

Arylglyoxal thiosemicarbazones or semicarbazones (8) : A mixture of appropriate fluorine containing arylglyoxal (0.01 mol) with thiosemicarbazide or semicarbazide (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 1 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was purified by crystallisation from carbon tetrachloride-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°). The physical data of the compounds are recorded in Table 2.

Fluorinated-5-aryl-3-hydroxy-1,2,4-triazines (9) : A mixture of an ethanolic (95%) solution of **8a** (2.09 g, 0.01 mol; 25 ml) and potassium carbonate (2.07 g, 0.015 mol) was refluxed for 6–8 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, filtered and the filtrate on acidification with HCl (2N) afforded **9a** as an orange-red solid which was crystallised from ethyl acetate. The physical data of the com-

pounds are recorded in Table 3.

 TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **8***

Compd no	Ar	X	Yield %	Mp °C
8a	4-F	Σ	74	185
b	4-F, 3-CH ₃	S	74	220d
c	2-F, 5-Cl ₃	S	68	187
d	3-Cl, 4-F	Σ	62	121
e	4-F	O	62	220δ
f	4-F, 3-CH ₃	O	62	187
g	2-F, 5-CH ₃	O	66	175

* All compounds gave satisfactory N, C and H analyses.

Fluorinated-2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole and/ -thiadiazole (10) : A mixture of 4-fluorophenylglyoxal semicarbazone (2.09 g, 0.01 mol), sodium acetate (1.23 g, 0.015 mol) and sodium bromide (1.54 g, 0.015 mol) in glacial acetic acid (70 ml) was refluxed for 6–8 h. On cooling, the resulting solid was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) mixture. The physical data of the compounds are recorded in Table 4.

Scheme 2

TABLE 3— PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 9 AND 10*

Compd no	Substituents in Ar	X	Yield %	Mp °C
9a	4-F	™	78	215
b	4-F, 3-CH ₃	—	78	220
c	2-F, 5-CH ₃	—	76	218
10a	4-F	O	64	210
b	4-F	Σ	68	200

* All compounds gave satisfactory N, C and H analyses.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. Dr. Dieter Enders, Institut für Organische Chemie der RWTH, Aachen, F.R.G. for his generous permission to record pmr and mass spectra. The financial help from U.G.C. and C.S.I.R., New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. G. E. WIEGAND, V. J. BAUER and S. R. SAFIR, *J. Med.*

Chem., 1969, **12**, 1969; V. WOLF and W. LOOP, Ger. Pat. 1 121 052/1962 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, **57**, 833); I. ITO, S. MURAKAMI and K. KATO, Jap. Pat. 7 015 733/1970 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, **73**, 77240); S. A. DAUSSE, Br. Pat. 1 106 679/1968 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1969, **69**, 59220); G. VIET, H. COUSE and G. MOUZIN, Ger. Pat. 2 810 052/1978 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **89**, 197609); C. RISTESCU and M. LAZARESCU, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1969, **14**, 797; F. SORM, A. ZAKUBONIC and L. SLECHTA, *Experientia*, 1950, **12**, 271; D. L. TREPANIER, US Pat. 3 780 039/1993 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, **80**, 96029); J. M. GULLO, W. P. HEILMAN, R. J. WAYNER and R. E. MOSSER, Ger. Pat. 2 821 381/1978 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, **90**, 12166); R. D. TRUST and J. D. ALBRIGHT, US Pat. 4 159 375/1979 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, **91**, 123758).

- K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and M. K. GOYAL, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1981, **18**, 1651; K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and M. K. GOYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 904.
- K. C. JOSHI and S. C. BAHTEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 121.
- K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and P. ARYA, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1977, **41**, 543; K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and P. ARYA, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1979, **43**, 199.
- B. BALZ and G. SCHIEMANN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1927, **60**, 1186.
- B. K. DIEP, N. P. BUU-HOI and N. D. XUONG, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2784.
- K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and S. K. JAIN, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1981, **1**, 159.
- D. YOUNG, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **93**, 1058.